

Summary of the joint GSI/ARIES-APEC “High Intensity RFQ meets Reality” Workshop held at Heidelberg in 2019¹

Workshop Organizing Panel

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The “High Intensity RFQ meets Reality” workshop was held in Heidelberg from 15 to 16 April 2019, jointly by the Gesellschaft für Schwerionenforschung (GSI) and by the EC co-funded ARIES Work Package 6 “APEC”. About 40 world experts hailing from key institutions attended ELOUD’18 with the following distribution – BNL:1, CERN: 3, FZJ: 1, Goethe University Frankfurt: 5, GSI: 16, Heidelberg Ion Beam Therapy Center: 1, IMP Lanzhou: 1, INFN LNL: 3, Marburg Ion Beam Therapy Center: 1, Max Planck Institute für Kernphysik: 2, Neue - Technologien GmbH & Co. KG: 1, NRS KI – ITEP: 1, ORNL: 1, Soreq: 1, NRC: 1, Toshiba Energy Systems: 1.

The workshop was composed of the following six sessions: 1) Experience from Operations; 2) Project Research & Development; 3) The Rise of the RFQ; 4) Beam Dynamics and Design; 5) Special Issues from Operations; and 6) Design, Construction and Production. The workshop agenda was tailored to embrace exchanges between the participants. Two major discussion sessions addressed comprehensive topics; four shorter time slots accommodated topical discussions.

All presentations are available on the workshop website at <https://indico.gsi.de/event/8575/> .

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Participants of the “High Intensity RFQ meets Reality” workshop at the Internationales Wissenschaftsforum Heidelberg.

Executive Summary

The workshop discussions highlighted important trends in the RFQ community.

With several decades of operational experience, the RFQ is a well-established subject. However, several participants pointed out the risk that **employee turnover** may soon cause an important loss of knowledge and experience. In consequence, the **sharing of operational experience between retiring staff and new arrivals** is regarded to be of uttermost importance, especially on the ground that the present performance of any RFQ is related to its history (design, production, operation), which is unique for each laboratory.

The participants agreed that the operation of an RFQ faces intrinsic technological difficulties, which impose trial and error procedures specific to each design. The reliability of an RFQ is also linked to the operational parameter set. **Establishing a set of parameter ranges that ensures a specific reliability** remains an open challenge.

The participants put particular emphasis on the issues of **surface quality and the surface preparation (conditioning)**. A visible degradation of the RFQ surface does not automatically yield a clear or observable impact on the rf- or beam-performance. After an involved discussion, the workshop concluded that the settings of parameters (e.g. voltages) in an RFQ are not a trivial procedure, and it should not be left to the arbitrariness of machine operators as the RF conditioning is a fundamental procedure to reach high RFQ performance. The assessment of surface damages is a critical R&D branch. The **correlation between surface damage and RFQ transmission** remains to be more clearly deciphered. Unanimously, RFQs should be opened as little as possible to minimise air exposure.

According to the experience of the participants, the **alignment of the rods and the quality of their fabrication** are among the essential factors defining the RFQ performance. The workshop also highlighted a **great impact of the ion-source stability on RFQ performance**. Another hotly debated topic was the **RFQ acceptance**, which greatly **depends on the operating regime** and on various beam parameters, in particular on the **beam current**.

The workshop talks and discussions also surveyed the beam-dynamics modelling tools with the conclusion that present codes work fine, and that the **predictability of RFQ performance is heavily affected by surface technology and surface conditioning**. **Comparing code predictions and experimental data** is further complicated by the **significant amounts of beam time** required to measure all relevant beam properties (one speaker reported that typically a month was necessary for a benchmarking measurement). This discussion on comparing code predictions with measurements was not entirely conclusive, e.g. **concerning the level of agreement between measurements and simulations which can be considered satisfactory**. Also the **relation between particle losses and emittance growth** requires further clarification. For example, several speakers indicated tens of % of emittance growth to be acceptable, while another talk showed significant changes in transmission already with variations at the few % level. A general agreement was reached that **particle losses inside the RFQ should be avoided**.

The discussions at the workshop uncovered a **potential origin of miscommunication between the ion source and the RFQ sectors**, namely, possibly different **standards of accuracy and quantitative precision** being traditionally employed by these two communities.

Most of the conveners agreed that even though the fundamental laws of physics governing the RFQ beam dynamics are well established, the **detailed differences between the plasma physics computations for ion sources, the modelling of the LEBT, and the simulations of beam dynamics through the RFQ can still be significant**. The workshop talks and discussions hinted that no generally accepted, common theory does yet exist, which would define the same relevant beam quantities for the ion source, the LEBT and the RFQ. Such **lack of common, identical parameters** may lead to discrepancies in the definition of technical terms, for example: 1) the emittance value depends on the beam distribution and can be calculated differently in the various parts of the accelerator, especially if this distribution features cross-plane correlations or non-Gaussian components; 2) for the Kilpatrick number, some of experts are taking into account the vane modulation, but some others do not.

As a final general synthesis, the performance of an RFQ is subject to the type of demands imposed by the accelerator construction project and/or by beam operations. A higher-performance RFQ requires a larger effort. **Reliability comes at the price of cost and with a more conservative design**.

The workshop discussions developed a list of **action items** such as compiling a **table with RFQ parameters** and a **list of codes used for RFQ modelling** including their specific features and references.

The audience proposed holding **another similar workshop in the not-too-distant future**, without a definite schedule yet, to follow up on the numerous actions and open questions.

Finally, it was proposed to condense the actual knowledge of RFQs into a comprehensive **review article for PRAB**, but this proposal did not gather universal support from the participants. Nevertheless, one or a few of the RFQ experts might want to pursue such a review article independently, benefitting from the wealth of information presented at the workshop, and as a great service to the worldwide community.